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D9.2 Community consultation and finalisation of Biodiversity FAIR data impact: Final data model and training materials completed and shared

Work Package	WP9 - Biodiversity
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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards

Executive summary

Biodiversity standards are essential for FAIR data, in particular for interoperability. Current standards need to be improved with new data models to better reflect the complexity of biodiversity and serve the information needed to address biodiversity loss and climate change. This Deliverable D9.2 is focussed on the results of Task 9.2: ‘Community consultation and finalisation of Biodiversity FAIR Data Impact’.

Facilitated via WorldFAIR, Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)’s engagement with the biodiversity community has led to this Deliverable – a new community-approved data standard that has progressed through a long community-led process. This Deliverable details the importance of collaboration and getting broad uptake of a new standard by the primary user community. This aligns with the overall objectives of WorldFAIR by focusing development on **improving the interoperability of biodiversity data**. Our FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP)¹ will be enhanced by this improved functionality. This work promotes cross-domain interaction as the Unified Data Model will enhance sharing of data in related Work Packages such as Agricultural Biodiversity, Oceans, and Geochemistry in the final portion of the WorldFAIR grant period. This work has been undertaken in alignment with the overall WorldFAIR goals, in particular WPO2 on Engagement, Synthesis, Recommendations and FAIR Assessment.

The new model, CamTrap DB, has been incorporated into the new and evolving GBIF Unified Data Model (see WorldFAIR D9.1). CamTrap DB is an important update to the previous camera trap data models. The use is growing of camera traps to non-invasively monitor biodiversity. Cameras are set in nature and take images of organisms with the resulting images being processed into GBIF occurrences - the evidence of a species at a particular place and time. Technologies have greatly improved in recent years and a plethora of new camera traps have been deployed, alongside the advent of AI technologies to more easily and rapidly identify organisms on the camera trap images. Camera traps are set to become major tools for biodiversity monitoring. In order to meet these goals, the image data management needed improvement: data management rather than data collection is now the limiting factor.

GBIF, through WorldFAIR, helped the camera trap research community rapidly take the updated model and facilitate adoption of best practices and the development of new GBIF infrastructure for FAIR data publication. This work is now adopted as part of the GBIF Unified Data Model. This work is an example of a research infrastructure facilitating a community standard development and making sure their best practices are codified and used within the research infrastructure.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

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1. Introduction

The improvement of data models to make data more FAIR is both a technical and social exercise. In WorldFAIR D9.1², a data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data was documented that focused on the technical aspect of model development. In D9.1 we described the development of the Event-based biodiversity model. The model was being driven by a use case approach that led to a conceptual model and eventually to a publishing model that allows the publication of FAIR data. The main examples given in D9.1 were around material collection data model development. In that case, GBIF drove the development of the case study and the ensuing conceptual and publishing models.

In Task 9.2, we describe the social aspect of data model development. A community of advanced camera trap users identified the need to improve their data model in response to improved technology and opportunities for monitoring biodiversity. They self-organised around the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) group to update the data model. In September 2021, GBIF ran a call³ for experts to prepare new or updated technical documentation from needs identified by GBIF. From this competition, GBIF funded updated guidance for camera trap best practices which is described in this report. This call was launched at an early stage of the development of the GBIF data model and the best practices and the data model work became aligned.

1.1. Camera traps

Camera traps have emerged as important tools for monitoring biodiversity in natural ecosystems. Camera traps are a non-invasive way to collect data - especially on mammals - on abundance, behaviour, and distribution of target organisms. They are relatively simple to deploy and can be placed so as not to disturb the organism being monitored. Technological improvements allow automatic triggering of images or video by motion detection. They also offer a view of animal behaviour that can potentially gather data on interaction events such as predation and pollination.

The growth of camera trap technology has advanced such that data management is now the limiting factor in their use in research. Responding to this, GBIF commissioned a guide to publishing camera trap data. This builds upon the community-led development of an updated camera trap model, CamTrap DB.

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

³

<https://www.gbif.org/news/35nbYlsHyZ9NWIFS2ySoEI/call-for-author-proposals-for-new-and-updated-gbif-technical-guides-closed>

1.2. Community process

By partnering with a community-led initiative and offering its services as funder, facilitator, and active adaptor, GBIF played an important role in finalising a new ‘best practice’ recommendation for the field which aligns and supports earlier WorldFAIR recommendations and efforts (Figure 1). These types of community partnerships are valuable for all parties involved, as the time required for a new data standard to go from idea to completion can be long and difficult. The improvement of data standards is often driven by an individual or a small group that has an idea and desire to improve a particular data type to become more FAIR, but lacks the funding and support to make this work a priority.

Figure 1. The process for a community accepted FAIR data model for camera trap data.

2. Camtrap DP: An open standard for the FAIR exchange and archiving of camera trap data

2.1. Camtrap DP

Camera Trap Data Package (Camtrap DP for short) is a Frictionless Data Package exchange standard format⁴ for camera trap data. It was developed by a community of users interested in improving camera trap data use⁵. Data and code are available at <https://github.com/tdwg/camtrap-dp>.

This development of improvements to CamTrap DP was accomplished by workers as part of their professional roles seeking to improve data. Both GBIF and our sister standard organisation, TDWG, the Biodiversity Information Standards group, supported the work with the expectation that the standard produced would be vetted by TDWG and implemented by GBIF. GBIF staff were authors but did not lead the publication. GBIF’s role, and that of WorldFAIR, was to fund later steps to fully

⁴ <https://specs.frictionlessdata.io/data-package/>

⁵ Bubnicki et al. 2023 <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2BC8J>

implement the new data model. GBIF funded the Best Practices document and built the software implementation pipeline needed for its application.

Current projects using Camtrap DP data model:

- camtraptor: R package to read, explore and visualise Camtrap DP.
- Agouti: Data management platform, uses Camtrap DP as export format.
- TRAPPER: Data management platform, uses Camtrap DP as export format.
- Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT): GBIF’s online software tool to publish biodiversity datasets.

2.2. Camtrap DP in the GBIF Unified Data Model

GBIF has incorporated Camtrap DP into its Unified Data Model⁶. The following section outlines how Camtrap DP has integrated into that larger model.

Figure 2. A simplified version of the Camera Trap Data Package physical data model intended to be captured as a Frictionless Data Package. Accompanying and describing this structure are the dataset metadata, which includes important dataset-wide information that also must be mapped.

A camera trap deployed in an area over a long period is used to detect and identify animals in sequences of images and in individual images within the camera's field of view. A camera takes

⁶ <https://www.gbif.org/new-data-model>

scheduled photos that are used to assess the functionality of the system. A camera begins an image sequence when triggered by movement. Multiple triggered sequences may be merged into one series post-facto. Artificial intelligence is used to make preliminary assertions about image contents (identification of individual animals, their sex, life stage, and taxonomic identification), and these are vetted and improved by groups of human experts.

2.2.1 Highlights of the model

Highlights of the model that provide a functional overview include the following points:

- An image is part of a sequence generated from zero or more detection events;
- Evidence of organism occurrences is based on image sequences;
- Organisms can be tracked within and between images and sequences;
- Artificial intelligence routines provide assertions, including identifications;
- A consensus identification of imaged organisms is made by a group of people;
- Identifications may be applied at the level of a sequence or at the level of an individual image.

Figure 3. A conceptual model covering the activities associated with a camera trap deployment, in which sequences result from detection triggers. Organism identification and Occurrence information are interpreted from images by artificial intelligence routines and vetted by human group consensus.

A deployment **Event** spans the period of time a camera is functioning properly in the field at a particular **Location** and may follow a specified **Protocol**. A sequence **Event** is triggered at the same **Location** as the deployment covering the field of view of the camera and spans a specific time period defining the bounds of the **Event**. Each sequence **Event** consists of one or more **StillImages** (each a **DigitalEntity**). An **Organism** (*sensu* Darwin Core; also an **Entity**) may be identified

(taxonomically and potentially as a recurring individual) within an image **sequence** or within one or more **StillImages**. These **Organism** observations infer a **Taxon** occurrence (an observation **Event**) at the same time and place as the parent sequence or image **Event**. The observed **Organisms** can have **Assertions** about the count of individuals, lifeStage, sex, behaviour, etc. Each **Organism** can be given one or more **Taxon Identifications** by expert groups and/or by artificial intelligence processes.

An arbitrary number of **Assertions** can be made about each class. **Assertions** can be quantitative or qualitative and can have **Assertions** made about them as well. **Agents** can have roles with respect to any class as well, including **Assertions**. These two common aspects of all use cases can be found in Common Models⁷.

The recommended publishing model is Camtrap DP (see <https://tdwg.github.io/camtrap-dp/>).

2.2.2 Mapping to the Unified Model

Below is a simple example that demonstrates the mappings from fundamental data in a Camtrap DP data set to the GBIF Unified Model. It is not expected that data publishers will have to do this mapping, as Camtrap DP would be the publishing model and GBIF would have to ingest Camtrap DP and transform it for internal representation. A much more thorough mapping based on example data from the Camtrap DP GitHub repository⁸ can be found in the camtrapdp folder⁹ of the GBIF model-tests GitHub repository.

Not shown are myriad fields in Camtrap DP that would be shared through Assertion tables attached to various tables in the GBIF Publishing Model. Also not shown are data from the data package metadata, all of which could also be mapped into the Unified Model to capture, for example, the Event associated with an entire project. The required Assertion tables that would be needed to transfer Camtrap DP datasets without loss are AgentAssertion, DigitalEntityAssertion, EventAssertion, IdentificationAssertion, OrganismAssertion, and TaxonAssertion.

2.3 Camtrap DP publishing model example

In this example (Table 1) there are two camera trap deployments, each at a distinct place and time period, as shown in the following table partially simulating the contents of the file deployment .csv in a Camtrap DP data set.

⁷ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZTMt-V3U0D0761bqqogeN58MjuHhIs_Kisu6CRtl-uA/edit#

⁸ <https://github.com/tdwg/camtrap-dp/tree/main/example>

⁹ <https://github.com/gbif/model-tests/tree/master/camtrapdp>

```
deployment.csv
deploymentID | start | end | locationID
----- | ----- | ----- | -----
dep1 | 2020-05-30T04:57:37+02:00 | 2020-07-01T11:41:41+02:00 | loc1
dep2 | 2020-07-29T07:29:41+02:00 | 2020-08-08T06:20:40+02:00 | loc2
```

Table 1. Example of Camtrap DP Publishing Model for two camera trap deployment.

In deployment dep1 (Table 2), a sequence seq1 was triggered and resulted in four images (med1, med2, med3 and med4) taken as shown in the following table partially simulating the contents of the file media.csv in a Camtrap DP data set. In deployment dep2, a sequence seq2 was triggered and resulted in four images (med5, med6, med7 and med8).

```
media.csv
mediaID | sequenceID | deploymentID | timestamp | filePath
----- | ----- | ----- | ----- | -----
med1 | seq1 | dep1 | 2020-06-05T20:00:00+02:00 | med1.jpg
med2 | seq1 | dep1 | 2020-06-05T20:00:02+02:00 | med2.jpg
med3 | seq1 | dep1 | 2020-06-05T20:00:04+02:00 | med3.jpg
med4 | seq1 | dep1 | 2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00 | med4.jpg
med5 | seq2 | dep2 | 2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00 | med5.jpg
med6 | seq2 | dep2 | 2020-08-05T03:20:42+02:00 | med6.jpg
med7 | seq2 | dep2 | 2020-08-05T03:20:44+02:00 | med7.jpg
med8 | seq2 | dep2 | 2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00 | med8.jpg
```

Table 2. Example of Camtrap DP Publishing Model media file structure.

In deployment dep1 observations were recorded at the level of media (Tables 3,4) partially simulating the contents of the file observations.csv in a Camtrap DP data set. In sequence seq1 the first image was determined by artificial intelligence to contain no targets of interest. In the second image in sequence seq1 there appears an adult Eurasian wild pig as identified by a person. In the third image in sequence seq1 an adult wild pig appears again, but with three additional juveniles, as identified by a person. In the fourth image in sequence seq1 there are no longer any targets of interest as determined by artificial intelligence.

In deployment dep2 observations were recorded at the level of sequences. In sequence seq2 there were two organisms of interest, an adult rat unidentifiable to species and an adult Tawny owl.

```
observations.csv
```

observationID	mediaID	sequenceID	scientificName	count	countNew	lifeStage	classificationMethod
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
obs1	med1	seq1	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	machine
obs2	med2	seq1	Sus scrofa	1	1	adult	human
obs3	med3	seq1	Sus scrofa	1	0	adult	human
obs4	med3	seq1	Sus scrofa	3	3	juvenile	human
obs5	med4	seq1	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	machine
obs6	NULL	seq2	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	machine
obs7	NULL	seq2	Rattus sp.	1	NULL	adult	human
obs8	NULL	seq2	Strix aluco	1	NULL	adult	human
obs9	NULL	seq2	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	machine

Table 3. Example of Camtrap DP Publishing Model observation file structure.

GBIF Unified Model Example

Event

eventID	eventType	parentEventID	eventDate	locationID
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
dep1	deployment	proj1	2020-05-30T04:57:37+02:00/2020-07-01T11:41:41+02:00	loc1
dep2	deployment	proj1	2020-07-29T07:29:41+02:00/2020-08-08T06:20:40+02:00	loc2
seq1	sequence	dep1	2020-06-05T20:00:00+02:00/2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00	loc1
seq2	sequence	dep2	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00/2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00	loc2
med1	image capture	seq1	2020-06-05T20:00:00+02:00	loc1
med2	image capture	seq1	2020-06-05T20:00:02+02:00	loc1
med3	image capture	seq1	2020-06-05T20:00:04+02:00	loc1
med4	image capture	seq1	2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00	loc1
med5	image capture	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00	loc2
med6	image capture	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:42+02:00	loc2
med7	image capture	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:44+02:00	loc2
med8	image capture	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00	loc2
obs1	observation	med1	2020-06-05T20:00:00+02:00	loc1
obs2	observation	med2	2020-06-05T20:00:02+02:00	loc1
obs3	observation	med3	2020-06-05T20:00:04+02:00	loc1
obs4	observation	med3	2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00	loc1
obs4	observation	med3	2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00	loc1
obs5	observation	med4	2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00	loc1
obs6	observation	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00/2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00	loc2
obs7	observation	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00/2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00	loc2
obs8	observation	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00/2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00	loc2
obs9	observation	seq2	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00/2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00	loc2

Entity

entityID	entityType	entityCreated
-----	-----	-----
<i>med1_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-06-05T20:00:00+02:00
<i>med2_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-06-05T20:00:02+02:00
<i>med3_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-06-05T20:00:04+02:00
<i>med4_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-06-05T20:00:06+02:00
<i>med5_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-08-05T03:20:40+02:00
<i>med6_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-08-05T03:20:42+02:00
<i>med7_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-08-05T03:20:44+02:00
<i>med8_digent</i>	DigitalEntity	2020-08-05T03:20:46+02:00
<i>organism1</i>	Organism	
<i>organism2</i>	Organism	
<i>organism3</i>	Organism	
<i>organism4</i>	Organism	

DigitalEntity

digitalEntityID	digitalEntityType	format	accessURI
-----	-----	-----	-----
<i>med1_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med1.jpg
<i>med2_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med2.jpg

<i>med3_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med3.jpg
<i>med4_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med4.jpg
<i>med5_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med5.jpg
<i>med6_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med6.jpg
<i>med7_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med7.jpg
<i>med8_digent</i>	StillImage	image/jpeg	med8.jpg

Organism

organismID	organismScope
-----	-----
<i>organism1</i>	individual
<i>organism2</i>	individual
<i>organism3</i>	individual
<i>organism4</i>	individual

EntityEvent

entityID	eventID
-----	-----
<i>med1_digent</i>	med1
<i>med2_digent</i>	med2
<i>med3_digent</i>	med3
<i>med4_digent</i>	med4
<i>med5_digent</i>	med5
<i>med6_digent</i>	med6
<i>med7_digent</i>	med7
<i>med8_digent</i>	med8
<i>organism1</i>	med2
<i>organism1</i>	med3
<i>organism2</i>	med4
<i>organism3</i>	seq2
<i>organism4</i>	seq2

EntityAssertion

entityAssertionID	entityID	entityAssertionType	entityAssertionValue	entityAssertionUnit
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
entityassertion1	organism1	count	1	individuals
entityassertion2	organism2	count	3	individuals
entityassertion3	organism3	count	1	individuals
entityassertion4	organism4	count	1	individuals
entityassertion5	organism1	lifeStage	adult	
entityassertion6	organism2	lifeStage	juvenile	
entityassertion7	organism3	lifeStage	adult	
entityassertion8	organism4	lifeStage	adult	

Identification

identificationID	identificationType	taxaFormula	verbatimIdentification
------------------	--------------------	-------------	------------------------

idID1	idID2	idID3	idID4
human	human	human	human
A	A	A sp.	A
Sus scrofa	Sus scrofa	Rattus sp.	Strix aluco

IdentificationEntity

identificationID	entityID
idID1	organism1
idID2	organism2
idID3	organism3
idID4	organism4

Taxon

taxonID	kingdom	scientificName
taxon1	Animalia	Sus scrofa Linneaus, 1758
taxon2	Animalia	Rattus Fischer de Waldheim, 1803
taxon3	Animalia	Strix aluco Linneaus, 1758

TaxonIdentification

taxonID	identificationID	taxonOrder
taxon1	idID1	1
taxon1	idID2	1
taxon2	idID3	1
taxon3	idID4	1

Table 4. Example of complete Camtrap DP Publishing Model when published for GBIF Unified Data Model.

These tables show the details that are captured in the data model. Previously, GBIF would have been only able to include the occurrence of the particular organisms. With this robust data, not only is the occurrence available but there is also other methodological information available for users.

3. Best practices for managing and publishing camera trap data

Periodically, when funding is available, GBIF calls for community input to improve its documentation to aid the publication of various types of biodiversity data. In September of 2021, GBIF ran a call¹⁰ for experts to prepare new or updated technical documentation from needs identified by GBIF. The community that developed Camtrap DP identified the need to improve their data model through

¹⁰

<https://www.gbif.org/news/35nbYlsHyz9NWIFS2ySoEl/call-for-author-proposals-for-new-and-updated-gbif-technical-guides-closed>

‘best practices’ documentation that would help align data publishers to mobilise FAIR camera trap data to GBIF.

This ‘best practices’ guide is a set of recommendations for camera trap data management and for publication to GBIF. The intended audience is data practitioners currently or considering using camera traps. Additional information in the guide is useful for data publishers and general biodiversity informaticists who share data with GBIF.

The guide focuses on these practical items:

- The use of camera traps
 - What are camera traps?
 - Why are camera traps used?
 - Camera trap project life cycle
- Managing camera trap data
 - What are camera trap data
 - Project Metadata
 - Media files
 - Deployments
 - Observations
 - Data management systems
- Publishing camera trap data
 - FAIR camera trap data
 - Preparing data
 - Camtrap DP
 - Darwin Core Archive

3.1. Best practices for publishing camera trap data to GBIF

3.1.1 Best practices documentation

As part of the larger GBIF data model and best practices development aligned with WorldFAIR, GBIF commissioned “Best Practices for Managing and Publishing Camera Trap Data.”

Authors: Lien Reyserhove, Ben Norton & Peter Desmet

Contributors: Tanja Milotic and Pieter Huybrechts

Suggested citation: Reyserhove L, Norton B & Desmet P (2023) Best Practices for Managing and Publishing Camera Trap Data. Community review draft. GBIF Secretariat: Copenhagen. <https://doi.org/10.35035/doc-0qzp-2x37>.

The Community Review draft document¹¹ was submitted for GBIF community review from 15 September until 31 October 2023.

3.2 Community consultation

3.2.1 Process

GBIF released draft technical documents for community peer review. Community members interested in contributing to this peer-review process could read the overview of the digital documentation programme¹² to place their efforts in context, then review the specific instructions and expectations on how to offer suggestions and improvements¹³.

To provide their voice and participate as a reviewer, GBIF asked community members to:

- Create a GitHub account (see video how-to¹⁴).
- Read the document, Best Practices for Managing and Publishing Camera Trap Data¹⁵
- If you see something, you can say something by creating or commenting on issues on GitHub¹⁶ (see video how-to¹⁷)
- Start, follow and support discussions on the GBIF Community Forum¹⁸

Reviewers were reminded that all interactions within this process must adhere to the GBIF Code of Conduct¹⁹, which aims to encourage a "safe, hospitable, and productive environment" that is "professional, respectful and harassment-free for all participating."

3.2.2 Community feedback

In this section we summarise the feedback received on the draft 'best practice' guide via the various channels for feedback that were made available to reviewers.

3.2.2.1 General feedback via GBIF community forum

¹¹ <https://docs.gbif-uat.org/camera-trap-guide/en>

¹² <https://docs.gbif.org/documentation-guidelines/en/>

¹³ <https://docs.gbif.org/contributing/en/>

¹⁴ <https://www.vimeo.com/430640810>

¹⁵ <https://docs.gbif-uat.org/camera-trap-guide/en/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/gbif/doc-camera-trap-guide/issues>

¹⁷ <https://vimeo.com/430632177>

¹⁸ <https://discourse.gbif.org/t/community-review-of-best-practices-for-managing-and-publishing-camera-trap-data/4149>

¹⁹

- No feedback was received on the GBIF Community Forum²⁰

3.2.2.2 General feedback via GitHub

- Prefer to see a gender-inclusive term instead of "manpower". Various guides suggest "workforce" and "human effort" as possibilities.
- Provide positive, "good" examples as well as bad examples, in a README document. It would give a template for users who might struggle with Table Schema.
- Provide a marine example to help buy-in from the marine community.
- Identification of typo and grammar clarifications.
- Reviewer suggested that a section placing camera traps in a broader context of camera and machine Observations (and explaining what those are) would be an improvement. Authors are considering this edit for the final draft.

3.2.2.3 Feedback on scope of work via GitHub

- Reviewer suggested relevance of identified camera trap images to training datasets for computer vision. Authors responded that indeed it is highly relevant but made distinction between releasing training datasets for computer vision and publishing camera trap datasets; the latter being the reason for the current document. Relevance to machine learning could be added.
- Current scope is for only fixed placed camera traps. Broader scope suggestions include:
 - Fixed-location insect cameras
 - Fixed-location underwater cameras
 - Moving drone (top-down) vegetation imaging
 - Moving underwater robot
 - Moving "Street View" like imaging of roadside/river vegetation
- A reviewer also suggested that one may be able to derive sample events from the observations. This is not always scientifically sensible, but processing may deliver these results (e.g. detection count, estimated individual count, percentage of marked individuals in detections, even biomass estimates).

While these are interesting ideas and may be pursued at a later time, they are not in scope of the current project.

²⁰ <https://discourse.gbif.org/t/community-review-of-best-practices-for-managing-and-publishing-camera-trap-data/4149>

3.2.2.4 Feedback on FAIR data principles via GitHub

One reviewer explicitly asked for a section outlining how the document makes camera trap data FAIR, stating “Publishing to a repository and using the GBIF network to publish data covers the F and the A of FAIR, but this document implicitly is a response to how to achieve the I and the R.” The reviewer then offered detailed text on what could be included. Authors responded that a section was originally considered but thought that much material is available. They are reconsidering for the final draft.

4. Frictionless data format for publishing camera trap data with GBIF’s Integrated Publishing Toolkit

The GBIF Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT)²¹ is a freely-available open-source web application that makes it easy to share four types of biodiversity-related information:

- primary taxon occurrence data
- taxon checklists
- sampling event data
- general metadata about data sources.

An IPT instance as well as the data and metadata registered through the IPT are connected to the GBIF Registry, are indexed for consultation via the GBIF network and portal, and are made accessible for public use. The IPT can also be configured with a DataCite²² account in order to assign DOIs to datasets, transforming it into a data repository.

In September 2023, the GBIF Secretariat made public a new release candidate²³ of the Integrated Publishing Toolkit. The new IPT was developed to aid publication of new datasets aligned to the new GBIF Unified Data Model²⁴. The release offers several evolutionary changes which are being described and added to the IPT User Manual²⁵. The release maintains all the functionality of previous versions of the IPT while accommodating richer data for testing environments by removing the constraints of the star schema at the heart of the Darwin Core Standard²⁶. The greater flexibility this enables support for new and emerging Frictionless Data Packages, in particular:

²¹ <https://www.gbif.org/ipt>

²² <https://datacite.org/>

²³ <https://ipt.gbif-uat.org/manual/en/ipt/latest/releases>

²⁴ <https://www.gbif.org/new-data-model>

²⁵ <https://ipt.gbif.org/manual/>

²⁶ https://www.gbif.org/standards#_darwin-core

- Camtrap DP²⁷, a community-developed data exchange format for camera trap data
- ColDP²⁸, a table-based exchange format used by the Catalogue of Life²⁹ and ChecklistBank³⁰

Changes introduced to IPT v3.0 should have minimal impact on current users as they will upload spreadsheets or connect to databases, just as they currently do. The IPT will also continue to perform key validation checks, including the existence and uniqueness of the necessary IDs, and ensure the integrity of relationships when generating Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A) files.

5. Community training videos and case studies

Training for general Unified Data Model concepts and access to all case studies can be found at the GBIF Common Model³¹ site. More materials will be added as the model matures and grows.

Videos of GBIF data model webinars:

- [Webinar 1: Introduction to the GBIF new data model](#)³²
- [Webinar 2: Exploring collection management systems](#)³³
- [Webinar 3: Exploring camera-trap data](#)³⁴
- [Webinar 4: Exploring eDNA data](#)³⁵
- [Webinar 5: Exploring interactions data on plant pollination](#)³⁶

GBIF provides training materials for the Integrated Publishing Toolkit. This concise 25 minute live demo³⁷ shows how a dataset gets properly published and registered through GBIF.org.

6. Conclusion

GBIF will continue developing the Unified Data Model along many similar pathways, as has been reported in the WorldFAIR grant. The GBIF focus for 2024 is ecological data including better

²⁷ <https://camtrap-dp.tdwg.org/>

²⁸ <https://github.com/CatalogueOfLife/coldp#name>

²⁹ <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.checklistbank.org/>

³¹

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZTMt-V3U0D0761bqqogeN58MjuHhls_Kisu6CRtl-uA/edit#heading=h.ngqg84ep1bpr

³² <https://www.gbif.org/composition/7AZMWZtLvrnfYbFpUdF83I>

³³ <https://www.gbif.org/composition/61cjmTVM6isZjq3WAvIt8A>

³⁴ <https://www.gbif.org/composition/4fZGV2vrXjo3rNxyS41sj>

³⁵

³⁶ <https://www.gbif.org/composition/6yJQMg2cvnnzb88xwt62m7>

³⁷

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eDH9IoTrMVE&embeds_referring_euri=https%3A%2F%2Fipt.gbif.org%2F&source_ve_path=OTY3MTQ&feature=emb_imp_woyt

interpretation of sampling event data. GBIF also hopes to start a trait data model prototype. These two areas are ripe for progress because they, like the camera trap community, already have advanced model development that should make them easier to include in the unified model.

In the WorldFAIR context, the collaboration between WPs 09 (this work package, Biodiversity) and 10 (Agricultural Biodiversity) has been productive in developing a functioning data publishing pipeline. This work could be expanded within the CDIF³⁸ work emerging from WorldFAIR, if the GBIF unified data model is useful in this regard.

The data publishing models, while exciting, are only half of the story. GBIF needs to complete building the databases to maintain the published data and more importantly the interfaces for users to access the data. This will begin with the material catalogue to be produced in 2024 with other outputs as resources and time allow. This will include understanding how users might want to access the data to ask new scientific questions. This undoubtedly will take many rounds of community input as GBIF exposes the new data and researchers identify how they would like to use this new opportunity.

To finish there is a very exciting opportunity in the GBIF data model that has not yet been broached – people. Almost every event and assertion in the model includes actions by a person. (A few are wholly completed by computer actions.) Credit for an individual's action can be woven into the model thereby providing the ability to give credit for actions. An individual should be able to see and quantify the impact of their actions. This work has not begun but can provide incentive for workers and funders alike.

³⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

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